

The Dischma mystery

**Working document by Bettina Schaefli, last update 26.10.2023, not all parts are regularly updated;
the document can be shared and will be made available on Zenodo**

Updated on 26. 10. 2023 with some more recent data (partial update only)

Updated on 06 March 2018 with simulations received from N. Wever, (SLF), T. Brauchli, EFPL

Updated on 30. 06. 2016 with simulations received from N. Griessinger, WSL, UNI-ZH

Updated on 21 March 2016 with HBV simulations received from M. Staudinger UNI-ZH

Conference presentation: <http://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2016/EGU2016-1624-3.pdf>

1 Preliminary comment

This is a working document. Some of the text has been written back in 2016. I checked the text for the latest version but did not update all the figures. The figures represent the data that I had on my computer when working on the different parts.

2 Context

While working on a paper (Schaepli, 2016), I tried very hard to get a good fit to the Dischma discharge data¹ after the year 2000. I noticed that even if I calibrate the SEHR-ECHO model (Schaepli et al., 2014) to the period 2000-2009, I get bad simulation performances for the period after 2001 (Figure 1). The Nash values (which should be close to 1) and the biases (water balance error) computed for all individual years of the simulation period (Figure 2) clearly show that something strange is going on after the year 2000, in particular in the **years 2001 and 2002** (calendar years). I spent a lot of time trying to solve the striking mismatch between data and simulations (Figure 1) with time variable model parameters, without conclusive results.

In this document, I try to identify the source of this model-data mismatch by first analysing the meteo data (Section 3), then the discharge data (Section 4), followed by a comparison of the discharge data with observations from other catchments (Section 5) and a comparison of the discharge simulations obtained from different models (Section 6), before drawing some conclusions (Section 7).

Figure 1: Simulated and observed discharge for the Dischma for the years 1992, 2005 (top row), 2001, 2002 (bottom row). Bad performance especially during the beginning of the spring melt for the years 2001 and 2002 is visible. Simulation Qsim1 is calibrated on 1983-1992, simulation Qsim2 is calibrated on 2000-2009. From figure_plotSEHREchoPerf.m.m fig_SEHRperf_2periods.tif

¹ For details on the gauging station, <https://www.hydrodaten.admin.ch/en/seen-und-fluesse/stations/2327>

Figure 2: Nash values computed between observed and simulated discharge per year (=sum of squared errors / sum of deviation of the observation from the mean) and the corresponding bias (difference between observed and simulated mean value divided by the mean observed value); period: 1983-2013. Source: figure_plotSEHREchoPerf.m fig_SEHR_NashBiasPerYear

3 Something wrong about the precipitation data?

The available model simulations in the Dischma catchment mainly use the Davos and Weissfluhjoch meteo stations. Their recording might not be representative for the Dischma meteo during this period. A look on the observed annual totals shows that the two meteo stations show similar annual trends for precipitation (Figure 3), which is, however, not reflected in the annual specific discharge (observed discharge in m^3/s divided by the catchment area and expressed in mm/year) (Figure 3). Besides these two meteo stations, Davos (DAV) and Weissfluhjoch (WFJ), there is the daily precipitation station Dischma (not often used for modelling), located close to the outlet at 1720 m asl., whose observations are close to the observations of DAV but somewhat different from the observations at WFJ, as visible from the yearly cumulative plots (Figure 4). Separating the observations at these three stations for the years before and after 1997 shows that the observed precipitation differs more for the latter period (Figure 5). But this difference in observed precipitation cannot explain the bad model performance. The next step is a comparison of annual precipitation totals to annual discharge (Figure 6). This analysis does not provide further insights since **discharge is overall higher than precipitation** observed at the meteo stations. This underestimation of total water input to the catchment is reproduced in the gridded precipitation data of MeteoSuisse, RhiresD (MeteoSwiss, 2011), which closely reproduces the meteo data at the Davos station (Figure 6, left) (for a paper on how good RhiresD is for hydrological modeling in Alpine areas, see the work of Freudiger et al., (2016)). **The small glacier present in the catchment (a few percent) cannot explain this underestimation.** The comparison of the gridded meteo product with the discharge totals (Figure 7), however, clearly highlights that there has to be an error in the discharge observations of the **year 2001**, which sticks out in the plot.

Figure 3: Top: five year-average of air temperature at Davos station and the temperature lapse rates between Davos and Weissfluhjoch (for the rather surprising temperature “step change”, see also (Reid et al., 2015)), center: five year-average of mean annual precipitation at the two stations and of the specific discharge; bottom: discharge divided by precipitation at the two stations (same legend as center); all values computed over moving windows of five years. From fig_meteo_DischmaDiffPeriods_fromHPpaper.m

Figure 4: Yearly double cumulative plots of daily precipitation at the three stations Davos (DAV), Weissfluhjoch (WFJ) and Dischma (DIS, daily time step only); dashed line is the 1:1 line; (source: plot_doublCumulPrecip.m)

Figure 5: Double cumulative plots of daily precipitation at the three stations Davos (DAV), Weissfluhjoch (WFJ) and Dischma (DIS, daily time step only) for two different periods; dashed line is the 1:1 line.

Figure 6: Left: Comparison of annual precipitation from station Davos and from station Weissfluhjoch vs annual discharge, and comparison precipitation at station Davos with gridded precip RhiresD, source, analysis on hydrological years starting on 01 oct; right: Comparison DAV data with gridded data, average over all grid cells contained in the catchment (source: PrecipTotals_vs_Q.tiff, dischDaily_analyseAnnualTotals.m. PrecipDav_vs_Rhires.tiff)

Figure 7: Observed mean annual discharge plotted against gridded mean annual precipitation (all grid cells contained in the catchment are averaged); left: without labels, right: with year labels (source: RhiresD_Q_Dischma_noLabels.tif, RhiresD_Q_Dischma_Labels.tif, analyseRhiresD_Dischma.m)

4 Analysis of the discharge data

4.1 Hourly discharge inspection

The analysis of precipitation and discharge data hints towards discharge data problems around the year 2001. A closer look on the hourly discharge data shows that there are data errors in 2004 (Figure 8): the discharge shows regular daily cycles throughout the year. These daily cycles might at a first glance be related to snow melt; comparison between the years shows a strong, unusual daily variability. The daily cycles are very too strong and last long in autumn².

Interestingly, 2004 was the first year when a pressure sensor was used (installed on 27 Oct 2003, replaced again in November 2006 and in September 2011, Andreas Kohler, Swiss Federal Office of the Environment, SFOE, personal communication, 12 October 2015). The data are clearly wrong in that year and a possible explanation would be a malfunctioning of the air pressure probe: the water pressure is deduced from the difference between the air pressure and the pressure in the water; if the air pressure probe malfunctions, this would typically result in unusual cycles (daily pressure has sub-daily variations³).

²I received the following information from Tobias Jonas, SLF on 10.11.15: He had a look into their SWE product for the entire region "Alpenrhein" and has seen that in 2004, there was an exceptionally high amount of snow late in Spring. Beginning June, there was even more snow than in 1999 and 2000. The reduction of the snowcover was very strong during June, which has certainly caused an exceptional inflow of meltwater. According to the SWE data, this should however have stopped around mid-July.

³ See e.g. <https://www.noaa.gov/jetstream/atmosphere/air-pressure>, last accessed on 26 Oct. 2023

Figure 8: Left: zoom on the hourly observed discharge at Dischma station for the year 200; right: hourly observed discharge at Dischma station for three periods of five years. The year 2004 clearly shows very different subdaily discharge fluctuations.

4.2 Analysis of the annual runoff ratio

We can compute the annual runoff ratio from the mean annual precipitation and the specific observed discharge. This runoff ratio has significantly changed over the years (Figure 9). Comparing the pattern of this runoff ratio to the pattern of Nash values (as a single proxy for model performance) reveals a striking similarity.

An actual decrease or increase of the annual runoff ratio would require a significant change of the hydrological processes that lead to a loss of water from the catchment: groundwater export (e.g. groundwater flow below the discharge gauging station), evaporation (e.g. of intercepted rainfall and snowfall), transpiration or anthropogenic water withdrawal. As can be seen from Figure 9, these changes would account for up to 300 mm/year, i.e. a quarter of the mean annual discharge, 1983-2014, of 1214 mm/year.

Significant vegetation changes (interception, transpiration) can be excluded. Groundwater by-pass of the discharge station is possible but would require a major modification of flow paths in the subsurface.

NOTE:

1. The runoff ratio computed from precipitation and discharge is slightly misleading because the system has a small glacier. This glacier can however not contribute enough water on an annual basis to change the picture. Even an extreme icemelt contribution of 2000 mm/year⁴ on the entire glacier area would represent only 4 % of the mean annual discharge (glacier area was around 2.4 % in 2000).
2. The above discussion is conditional on the assumption that the representativity of the Weissfluhjoch station for the catchment has not evolved over the period.

⁴ The Swiss-wide average glacier mass change relative to the average glacier surface for the period 1980 – 2010 is estimated to -0.62 mm water equivalent/year Fischer, M., Huss, M., and Hoelzle, M.: Surface elevation and mass changes of all Swiss glaciers 1980-2010, Cryosphere, 9, 525-540, 10.5194/tc-9-525-2015, 2015.

Figure 9: Top: Nash values (SEHR-ECHO simulation calibrated on 1983-1992) and annual runoff ratios computed as the mean specific observed discharge (mm/years) divided by the mean annual precipitation at Weissfluhjoch station (mm/years). The pattern would look very similar for the Davos station. Bottom: mean discharge – mean precipitation at Weissfluhjoch. The values are computed over moving windows of five years, centred on the reference year. From: figure_plotSEHREchoPerf.m, fig_SEHR_Nash_RunoffRatio

5 Comparison of discharge data with other catchments

5.1 Double mass plots of nested catchments

The Dischma is a tributary of the Landwasser river. The Landwasser has some run-of-river hydropower influence, which should not impact that analysis that follows.

The comparison of the cumulative discharge of the Dischma and the Landwasser seems to support the hypothesis that the Dischma has observational problems for the years 1999 – 2004: for these years, the cumulated discharges of two rivers clearly diverge (Figure 10), for calendar years as well as hydrological years and even in terms of normalized flow (which emphasizes pattern differences, Figure 10 right column). A double mass analysis of the period 1974-2018 shows that in terms of annual totals, only the years 2001 and perhaps 2002 behave differently for the Dischma discharge station than for the Landwasser station. Thereafter, the relationship returns to the one before 2000 (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Double cumulative plots of the Dischma and the Landwasser discharge (Dischma, 43.3 km², is a tributary of the Landwasser 183 km²); left column: without normalization, right: with normalization to 1; top: year starting on 01 Jan, bottom: year starting on 01 Oct.

Figure 11: Double cumulative plots of the Dischma and the Landwasser for the period 1974 to 2018; the linear interpolation is fitted to the data 1974-2000; the blue data portion are the years 2001 and 2002; from analyse_DB_Hydro.m, doubleMass_dischma_landwasser_1974_2018

5.2 Comparison with discharge observations in other catchments

We can also compare mean annual discharge anomalies (mean annual values minus the long-term mean) with those from similar catchments, eg. the ones depicted in Figure 12 (gauged catchments with similar hydroclimatic conditions and undisturbed flow). The comparison of the anomalies (Figure 13) clearly suggests that the Dischma discharge recordings do not follow the trends of the other catchments for the years 2001-2006. The analysis also reveals that Krumbach has a different behavior after 2007 (Figure 13 top) and that the Poschiavino had a different behavior somewhere around 1987 (Figure 13 bottom).

Figure 12: Location of comparison catchments

Figure 13: Top: Comparison of observed and simulated annual discharge *anomalies* for the Dischma river with annual discharge anomalies from four rivers with similar hydrologic regime, catchment size and glacier cover (the Krumbach river has some missing data). Bottom: updated figure – comparison over a longer period with the additional river **Ova dal Fuorn**, **Krumbach** excluded. The averages are smoothed over 5 years, the anomalies are obtained by dividing by the mean over the entire period considered here; from figure_compareQobsWithOtherCatchmentsV1.m; and figure_compareQobsWithOtherCatchmentsV2.m

6 Comparison with model outputs

In the context of detecting model errors, I tried to compare my own discharge simulations with those completed by other groups with other models. Available are:

- PREVAH and HBV simulations from (Orth et al., 2015), period 1987 - 2009⁵, validation period 2002-2009
- HBV simulations of (Jenicek et al., 2016)⁶, validation period (check publication)
- Unpublished Alpine3D simulations available from Nander Wever (2005- Oct. 2014), calibrated on 2005-2009⁷, (check if they used Weissfluhjoch precipitation data)
- Unpublished Alpine3D simulations available from Tristan Brauchli (2001-2016), calibrated on xxxxx (update), used improved precipitation distribution method, based on Davos observed precipitation (check)
- HBV (HBV light) simulations from (Griessinger et al., 2016) who used external snow data to improve the model performance, available period 1998 – 2013.
- SEHR-ECHO simulations that use Weissfluhjoch precipitation

Focusing on the mean annual discharge, we see that the SEHR-ECHO simulations (calibrated on 2000-2009, called SEHR-ECHO-0009), as well as the PREVAH and HBV simulations from Orth et al., (2015) and the HBV simulations of Jenicek et al. (Jenicek et al., 2016) and of Griessinger et al. (2016) completely drift away from the observed discharge *anomalies* (Figure 13)(the anomalies are obtained by dividing the simulation by the mean over the entire considered period).

It can be seen that the SEHR-ECHO-0009 model comes closer to the observed data than the other simulations (Figure 13), which is NOT due to the fact that it is calibrated on the period 2000 -2009 (see Figure 15). Note that in (Orth et al., 2015), the period after 2002 it is the validation period. For the simulations of Griessinger et al. (2016) the calibration and the validation period are not continuous over the entire available period (1998 – 2013).

The Alpine3D simulations of Wever started only after 2005. The meltwater runoff transform is calibrated, which does, however, not affect the amount of total flow in the system. It can be seen that this simulation is very close to the observed flow for the calibration period (2005-2009) and thereafter.

The Alpine3D simulations of Brauchli started in 2001. The meltwater runoff transform is also calibrated; these simulations use a different precipitation input scheme than the Wever simulations(Brauchli et al.). These simulations are close to observations for the entire simulated period, but do not cover the period with the significant divergence of all models from observations.

⁵ Received from M. Zappa, WSL

⁶ Received from M. Staudinger, UniZH

⁷ Taking flow at 30cm soil depth as input into runoff transform module (does not influence the annual river flow); A3D setup: - Driven by the several IMIS stations in the area;- Precipitation interpolated with the altitudinal gradient, based on the heated rain gauge in Davos and at the Weissfluhjoch.- Richards equation for soil; - Bucket scheme for snow (due to computational constraints)

Given how close these simulations are to the observed data, longer time series might well shed light on the question on the quality of the discharge data. This analysis should be continued since there might well be new simulations available.

IMPORTANT: When extending the window of comparison to before 1990 and after 2009 (SEHR-ECHO-0009 available from 1983-2015, HBV- Jenicek from 1971-2012), it can be seen that in absolute discharge terms, these two simulations are just as far away from the observations during the period 1987-1993 as after 2001⁸, in terms of anomalies they are somewhat closer (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Comparison of observed and simulated annual discharge anomalies for the Dischma river, moving average over 5 years. The anomalies are obtained by dividing by the mean over the period considered here; the empty space on the left is just for the legend to fit into the same frame; from figure_compareQsimWithOtherModelsV2.m (figure title should be "5 years")

Figure 15: Top: comparison of observed and simulated annual discharge for one HBV simulation and the SEHR-ECHO simulation; Bottom: comparison of anomalies; source: figure_compQsim_SEHR_2periods_HBVjenicek.m, , fig_compQsim_SEHR2periods_HBV.tif

⁸ Attention: the exact reference years depend on the smoothing window

7 Conclusions

We have identified individual years that have obvious discharge data problems, based on discharge and precipitation data analysis and comparison with other catchments. The year 2001 has clearly an issue with the total discharge (Figure 7). The double mass analysis of Dischma versus Landwasser suggests that during the hydrological years 1998/1999 to 2001/2002, the recorded discharge was very different for the two rivers. In the year 2004, the pressure sensor was most probably not properly working, which shows up in the hourly data but not in the double mass analysis. Comparison with discharge from similar catchments underlines that discharge observations could be wrong for the entire period 1999 to 2006 (but the exact duration of the period is difficult to determine due to the visual analysis based on a moving average). Furthermore, none of the conceptual models can reproduce the discharge for that period. Instead, these models simulate the same temporal dynamics for the Dischma as observed in the comparison catchments (compare Figure 13 and Figure 14), with an annual discharge dip around 2005.

Regarding the model analysis, we should keep in mind the following: All relatively simple models agree on not reproducing the data; this should be interpreted with care: they all have a very similar snow model. Longer Alpine3D (physical model) simulations might give additional insights.

At this stage, we can, thus, not be entirely sure that the discharge observations are wrong (except for the two critical years 2001 and 2004). The following phenomena could also explain the discrepancies between the models and the data or between the data from different catchments:

- Dynamically changing groundwater flow paths: the models have a slow subsurface flow component but do not explicitly model groundwater recharge dynamics and cannot model explicitly groundwater export out of the catchment
- Very different meteorological conditions in the higher part of the Dischma catchment than at the WFJ station or the DAV station. This hypothesis could be further investigated by analyzing radar data and the MeteoSwiss product CombiPrecip.

7.1 Some comments on potential observational errors

The hourly discharge series has every now and then wrong observations (e.g. extremely low discharge values in the middle of the summer in several years). In 1987, this happened repeatedly. These values might either be observational errors or might result from avalanches or landslides that block the river flow during a short period before causing a discharge peak (when the damming is removed). Such phenomena are frequent here (Tobias Jonas, personal information, Nov. 2015); they are, however, not very likely to last only an hour or two but might rather influence the discharge up to several days.

Another classical source of error is freezing of the river water or the measurement device itself. These errors only occur in winter. Such errors are easily visible in the winter low flow recordings (e.g. constant slow increase of the water level) and are probably corrected during data screening.

7.2 Some comments on the meteo stations

One source of uncertainty might be the non-homogeneity of the meteorological observations. I contacted Thomas Konzelmann from MeteoSwiss (responsible for ground stations), who told me that the stations did not experience any significant modifications during the considered period (personal communication, 18.11.15 and 23.11.15), even if a slope break is visible in the double cumulative plots (Figure 5). It is evident that the order of magnitude of these differences is not big enough to create the important difference between the model simulations and observed discharge during the critical years.

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